

FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES OF THE ISLAMIC BANK

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Annotation. *The relevance of the topic of the Islamic economy in general and the banking system in particular is gaining momentum, because the current financial situation in the world is forcing an increasing number of economists and politicians to think about the need to find new principles and tools.*

Key words. *islamic, financy, murabah, bank*

In recent years, Islamic business institutions have become an important component of the economies not only of Muslim states, but also of Western European countries. Among the financial and economic structures that have gone beyond the Muslim world are banks, insurance companies, investment funds. The geographical scope of these institutions is so wide today that for several years large European financial institutions have been using their financial know-how to develop products that meet the requirements of Sharia. And this process has its objective reasons. In addition to the successes achieved in recent years by the economies of Islamic states with the prevailing high oil prices, it is also the growth of the number of Muslims in the world. Thus, in Europe, due to the depopulation of the indigenous population in many countries, the proportion of Muslims is growing. Already today in Amsterdam, The Hague and Rotterdam, Muslims make up 60% of the population under 20 years of age. And in some areas of large cities in Germany, the proportion of Muslims is 40-50%. Therefore, the desire of European banks to open Islamic windows looks quite pragmatic. This is business and nothing else.

It should be noted that the creators of Islamic credit institutions have to overcome many obstacles. Thus, in modern literature there is a view of Islamic banking as an artificial phenomenon, which is a consequence of religious fanaticism and has nothing to do with economic expediency. In this regard, representatives of the International Association of Islamic Banks were forced to make a statement that they are not fanatics, but consider it their task to involve the

population with the Islamic faith in the accumulation process in order to accelerate social and economic progress. In our opinion, Islamic credit institutions cannot be interpreted as an artificial phenomenon caused by the arbitrary actions of their creators. In fact, prototypes of these institutions became widespread in the Muslim world as early as the XII century. At first, these were trading houses, in which banking operations began to focus. They functioned on the basis of the Islamic principle of "musharaka" - complicity, and one of the most common forms of the principle of complicity was "kyrad" - lending, i.e. the conclusion of an agreement between the owner of property or money and the direct executor of the trade operation. Even earlier, payment instruments such as bills of exchange, credit letters, etc. were widely used, which indicated a fairly high level of development of credit and financial relations in the Islamic economy.

However, Islamic credit institutions, unlike commercial banks, did not immediately reach the modern level of development due to the fact that during the colonial period, samples of credit system institutions introduced from Western states were most widespread. Islamic banks also include credit institutions that carry out their passive and active operations in accordance with the provisions of Sharia. Representatives of the most diverse currents of Islam are basically united in condemning and strictly prohibiting loan interest - riba, since it is closely related to usury. Interest in Islam is clearly separated from commercial profit, which is not prohibited. So, merchants are not condemned, but on the contrary, are encouraged due to the fact that they offer the buyer a product in which they have invested their professional skills, labor and capital. The commercial profit of merchants is the result of risk and effort. In addition, the merchant receives a profit at a time, at the time of the transaction. From the point of view of Islam, any wealth is permissible only if it is acquired by one's own labor or skills. In view of this, the fee for abstaining for a time from using or investing capital in the form of interest is prohibited and is replaced by participation in profits. The profit sharing system, which replaces the loan interest, seems to be nothing more than an expression of the Islamic principle of ensuring social justice in the economy, assuming a fair distribution of material benefits. This principle is an expression of the civilizational aspect in the evolution of the Islamic world.

It should be noted that Islamic banks provide a wide range of modern banking services. These are domestic and international transfers, collection of bills of exchange, letters of guarantee, traveler's checks, purchase and sale of currency at the rate of cash transactions "SPOT" (with immediate delivery), as well as precious metals. According to these services, a fee is charged to cover operating

expenses, in addition, Islamic banks provide a wide range of banking consulting and trust services. These are property management, consulting and expertise on projects, organization of stock subscriptions for the company, purchase and sale of shares on behalf of clients, credit card service. These services are performed in compliance with the provisions of Islam.

The next type of Islamic banking activity is the financing of murabaha trade (sale on credit). According to the given method of financing, the client applies to the bank with a request to purchase certain goods or property for him, and he himself undertakes, in turn, to buy them from the bank for a large amount. From this, the bank's profit is formed. The financing of murabah in its scheme resembles an operation on a documentary letter of credit. However, in accordance with Islamic principles, in a murabaha-type contract, the client is not legally obliged to buy goods from the bank, and therefore the bank assumes the risk covered if the client purchases this product or property from the bank.

Thus, Islamic banks use methods of Financing in accordance with Sharia in credit transactions of different types and varying degrees of urgency. At the same time, as already noted, there is a fairly pronounced specialization of Islamic financial institutions.

The problem of adapting the Islamic credit mechanism to the conditions of the modern market economy includes the question of the permissible level of loan fees, which at different stages of development, apparently, could be adjusted taking into account the contribution of Islamic credit institutions to the development of the general economic potential of society, the economic situation, etc. It seems that the share of profit from the participation of an Islamic bank in the operation being credited may increase, since it still does not mean receiving a fixed percentage, but in fact represents profit from joint venture.

Since it is unlikely that there will be a complete copying of Western development models in Islamic countries, it is obvious that Islamic credit institutions will continue to function in the future. It is quite possible that their sphere of activity will even expand due to the improvement of the mechanism of operations, taking into account the requirements of modernity. However, it seems unlikely that Islamic banks will completely replace conventional, for example, commercial banks.

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